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Lectures

New Insights on The Peacock Eye Disease Etiology

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Peacock eye disease is caused by the pathogenic fungus *Venturia oleaginea*. Despite substantial research, attempts to manage the disease in Israel have failed, leading to defoliation and yield losses. The long-term aim of this research was to develop a Decision Support System (DSS) to effectively control the disease. First, we studied the disease etiology in naturally infected olive groves of the susceptible cultivar ‘Souri’. Our results suggested that there are two periods within a season when infection events occur. The first occurs at the end of the autumn-beginning of the winter (October-November). Young leaves, formed in the autumn, exhibit disease symptoms in December-January, 1-3 months post-infection. Mature leaves, formed in the previous spring, exhibit disease symptoms in March-April, 2-4 months post-infection. The second infection occurs at the end of winter-beginning of spring (March-May). Symptoms develop on the infected leaves only in the following season, in January-February, 6-8 months post-infection. To validate these findings, we artificially infected olive trees in containers at two different periods, and we monitored disease progress on young and mature leaves. The results of this experiment corroborated with those observed in the commercial groves. *In vitro* experiments revealed that low temperatures restrict conidia germination and preclude the occurrence of infection in the winter. Our findings indicate that Peacock eye disease follows a monocyclic life cycle in Israel. Based on these insights we developed a DSS named ‘Tavazit’ designed to predict infections which can be used to optimize the timing of fungicide application in Israel.

Olive fruit rot (Dalmatian disease): a tree fungus that loves fruit

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The Dalmatian disease in olive trees (*Olea europaea*) is common throughout the Mediterranean basin and is caused by the fungus *Botryosphaeria dothidea* (anamorph *Fusicoccum aesculi*). The disease was recorded as early as 1883 in Dalmatia, Croatia, but the taxonomic identity of the fungal agent of the disease became clear only in 2004 on the basis of multiple molecular alignments. The fungus is known worldly mainly as an endophyte or as a latent pathogen in hundreds of types of trees. It often causes dieback and stem cankers in its host. The fungus is also the agent of a severe disease in apples, "Apple ring rot" as well as other fruit decays in storage conditions. In Israel the disease in olive has been suspected plantations for many years. However, the fungus was identified for the first time in 2019 as the cause of collapse of vines in the Rosh Pina area, and in 2022 as the cause of the olive fruit rot disease in the West of Sharon and in the Hadera area. The damage to the disease was observed mainly in olive vineyards harboring populations of the olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*) together with a parasitic wasp of the *Eupelmus* genus. The symptoms of the disease include rotting and desiccation of fruits with characteristic sunken cankers and the appearance of black fruiting bodies of the fungus (pycnidia) which consist a new source of infection. Contrary to what is known in the world, the fungus has not been detected in tissue of trees bearing diseased fruits. The correlation between the fungal infection and the olive fly along with the absence of the fungus from the infected tree tissues raises questions about the biology of the olive fruit rot disease in Israel.

Can algae save our valuable vines?

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Microalgae are known to produce antimicrobial compounds, yet studies on their efficacy against plant pathogens are limited. This research aims to study the efficacy of microalgal extracts from the Sea of Galilee against *Plasmopara viticola*, the causal agent of grapevine downy mildew disease. Preventive spray treatment with extracts from three algal species, C1, P1, and M1, at a concentration of 2,000 ppm, reduced the development of grapevine downy mildew symptoms on leaf discs by 67%, 73%, and 97%, respectively, compared to untreated control leaves. Subsequent preventive spraying of M1 algal extract at concentrations of 2,000, 1,500, and 1,000 ppm reduced disease symptoms by 99%, 71%, and 82%, respectively, compared to the control treatment. An examination of the extract's mode of action included its effects on zoospore release and motility *in vitro*. A concentration of 1,000 ppm completely inhibited the release of zoospores from sporangia, while 500 ppm achieved a 66% reduction. Moreover, only 10 ppm was necessary to prevent zoospore motility. One of the inhibition mechanisms of *P. viticola* may be related to impairing the release and motility of zoospores. The efficacy discrepancy between the *in vitro* and leaf assays likely stems from the requirement for direct contact with zoospores. Isolated compounds from the extract inhibited zoospores at concentrations below 50 ppm. Preliminary formulations of these substances, applied preventively on grape seedlings and in a field trial, inhibited disease symptoms by more than 80%. Future research aims to refine this formulation and the timing of application, extending to other oomycetes and advancing sustainable plant disease management.

The polyphenolic suberized peridermal skin of the Sikkim cucumber acts as an effective chemical barrier against *Botrytis cinerea* infection

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Certain species of fleshy fruit that undergo skin cracking are capable of forming a specialized polyphenolic periderm to seal the wounded skin. Some of the genetic and metabolic components pertaining periderm formation have been identified, however it remains unknown if, and to what extent, this specialized tissue can act as an efficient barrier against the invasion of pathogenic fungi. We monitored the infection process of *Botrytis cinerea* on the cuticle-coated skin of the common cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) or on the polyphenolic suberized peridermal skin of the Sikkim cucumber (*C. sativus* var. *sikkimensis*). *In vivo* inoculation assays inferred that while *B. cinerea* can successfully penetrate and form necrotic lesions on *sativus* fruit, it is incapable of penetrating the peridermal skin of *sikkimensis* fruit. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) profiling of fruit skin extracts, *in vitro* conidial germination and germ tube elongation assays, and qRT-PCR cutinase-encoding gene expression analyses, inferred that the accumulation of suberin monomers in the peridermal skin of *sikkimensis* fruit stimulate increased elongation of *B. cinerea* germ tubes and significantly alters the differential expression of cutinase-encoding genes. Among them, *Bcin0607010*, *Bcin08g01580* and *Bcin07g06480*, three yet unidentified cutinases, whose expression is specifically increased in the presence of *sikkimensis* fruit skin extracts. Our data demonstrate that a polyphenolic suberized peridermal skin in cucumber fruit can shape the interactions with *B. cinerea* and implies that suberization of fleshy fruit may provide a means for reducing damage imposed by this and other pathogens.

Tomato pith necrosis disease exhibits a synergistic interaction with Tomato Brown Rugose Fruit Virus (ToBRFV) and Pepino Mosaic Virus (PepMV) infections

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Over the past decade, the emergence of Tomato Brown Rugose Fruit Virus (ToBRFV) has significantly increased its prevalence in tomato greenhouses, causing a devastating impact on Israel's tomato industry. Concurrently with the emergence of ToBRFV, there has been a notable increase in pith necrosis in greenhouse tomatoes. Pith necrosis manifests as expanding inner rot in stem tissues and has traditionally been regarded as a marginal disease primarily caused by soil-borne opportunistic *Pseudomonads*. We hypothesized that ToBRFV infection might facilitate opportunistic infections by other pathogens, providing a potential explanation for the increase in pith necrosis incidences. To test this, we collected pith necrosis-symptomatic tomato plants from greenhouses in southern and central Israel during 2021-2023. The collected samples were tested for the presence of viral infections, specifically ToBRFV and Pepino Mosaic Virus (PepMV), and underwent bacterial isolation and identification through RpoB sequencing. Most samples were positive for either ToBRFV, PepMV, or both, and typically contained high inocula of bacteria from diverse lineages, including reported causal agents of pith necrosis such as *Pectobacterium*, *P. mediterranea*, and *P. viridiflava*. Inoculating naive tomato plants with pith necrosis-associated bacteria alone typically resulted in localized lesions that failed to expand beyond the area of inoculation or showed no symptoms. However, co-infection of *Pseudomonas* isolates with PepMV and ToBRFV led to expanded rot along the inner stem, which was significantly larger than the one observed during bacterial infection alone. Our data supports that tomato viral infection increase susceptibility to pith necrosis caused by opportunistic *Pseudomonads*.

Characterization and genetic mapping of melon plants resistance to the fungus *Macrophomina phaseolina*

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Macrophomina phaseolina is an Ascomycota fungus that attacks many hosts. In melon, the fungus causes the charcoal rot disease which expressed as wilting of the plant at fruit ripening and causes a severe economic loss. Today, the ways of management of the disease include using of grafting of melon scions onto resistant rootstocks of Cucurbita and soil fungicides, an expensive and polluting solution. The use of resistant varieties is an efficient solution, but currently, there are no commercially resistant melon varieties. Therefore, characterizing the existing diversity in melon and genetic mapping of the trait are necessary steps towards developing a resistant varieties. This is a complex trait due to the variable development of the disease across various growth conditions. To date, there has been no reports of genetic mapping of resistance to macrophomina, only characterization of variation across melon lines. The goal of the current research is characterization and mapping of macrophomina resistance in melon. In our laboratory, there is a broad and diverse collection of melon lines, from which a core set of 25 lines representing the overall diversity in the melon, was selected. The core lines underwent complete genome sequencing and were used to construct a library of 300 segregating populations for trait mapping. According to the results from previous experiments and ongoing experiments during this research, the 25 lines were characterized for disease resistance, and three populations from cross of resistant and susceptible parent were selected for trait mapping. In July 2023, a pots experiment was conducted on the first population, testing around 105 accessions on F5 generation. After inoculation and phenotypic characterization, 18 lines that showed the highest susceptible and 24 lines showed the highest resistance were selected. following DNA sequencing and primary data analysis, 4 Quantitative Trait Loci (QTLs) were found on chromosomes 3, 4, 6, and 8, demonstrating a significant association with the trait.

A pan-genomics AI-based algorithm for the prediction of type-III secretion system effectors

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Machine-learning algorithms are widely used to predict type III effectors (T3Es) in both animal and plant bacterial pathogens. We have previously developed Effectidor - a web server (freely available at <https://effectidor.tau.ac.il>), which classifies each ORF within a genome to either a T3E or not, based on a set of features such as the presence of regulatory elements in the upstream region of the ORF in question, its amino-acid composition, its sequence similarity to previously identified T3Es, to name a few. Here we extended Effectidor to analyze pan-genomes (up to 400 genomes simultaneously). The joint information from hundreds of genomes not only provides more accurate predictions, but also allows the inference of effectors evolutionary dynamics across the pan genome, e.g., the identification of core T3Es. In addition, the new version of Effectidor provides the subtype(s) of the encoded type III secretion systems (T3SSs). The minimal requirement to run the web server is a single genomic sequence. However, more accurate predictions can be obtained using advanced options, e.g., by including proteomes of closely related bacteria that do not encode a T3SS and by providing data on host proteomes.

Hybrid grapevine resistance to downy and powdery mildew in Israel and their sensitivity to invertebrate pests

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Powdery-mildew (PM, *Plasmopara viticola*) and Downy-mildew (DM, *Erysiphe necator*) in grapevine are foliar diseases that were introduced to Europe in the 19th century. As there was no co-evolution between those diseases and the European *Vitis*, all *V. Vinifera* cultivars are susceptible whereas American and Asian *Vitis* species differ in their susceptibility. Several breeding programs worldwide introduce resistance factors and create European-like resistant cultivars. *V. vinifera* However, co-evolved with several “local” pests including pathogens and invertebrates. Recently, resistant hybrid cultivars have been brought to Israel from Weinbauinstitut Freiburg (WBI, Germany) breeding programs to test their suitability to Israel's local climate conditions. Results: (i) In the lab and in the field the hybrid grapevine varieties: Bronner, Suvignier-Gris, Prior, and Cabernet-Carbon were found to be significantly less sensitive to PM and DM than the control *V. vinifera* varieties. (ii) Salicylic acid (SA) and Quercetin-3-glucuronide (Q3G) concentrations were higher in the tolerant varieties compared with Tempranillo (*V. vinifera*) leaves. (iii) *Colomerus vitis* galls incidence was significantly lower in Cabernet-Carbon compared with Suvignier-gris, Prior and Tempranillo. In one of the plots thrips (*Scirtothrips citri*) population was highest in Tempranillo but this could be due to its higher vigour. Here, we show that the hybrid varieties have high resistance to PM and DM, accompanied by a significant increase in SA and Q3G, metabolites that are associated with defense mechanism. However, besides looking at the hybrid variety agronomic traits, it's important to define the interactions with other possible pests that might need more control measures.

For better or worse - the effect of interspecies microbial interactions on disease severity in plants

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The ability to move on solid surfaces provides bacteria ecological advantages, such as facilitating nutrient acquisition or avoiding unfavorable environments. However, many bacterial species lack this trait. Previous studies have revealed that non-swarming bacteria can exploit the motility traits of neighboring species by hitchhiking on them. The described study explores the interplay between a phytopathogenic bacterium and a non-pathogenic swarming bacterium and examines how these interactions influence plant health. Using *Acidovorax citrulli* and *Paenibacillus* spp. as models, we show that, *in vitro*, *A. citrulli* can spread on solid surfaces by hitchhiking on *P. glucanolyticus* swarms. Conversely, when inoculated in proximity to *P. dendritiformis* cells with antibacterial activity, growth inhibition of *A. citrulli* was observed with no apparent spreading. In line with the aforementioned results, we show that when inoculated on plants, the interaction of *Paenibacillus* spp. swarms with the pathogen could have two opposing effects on plant health. The outcome could either be harmful or helpful to the plant, depending on the characteristics of the *Paenibacillus* species in the swarm. Our results suggest that interspecies interactions in mixed populations can significantly affect plant disease outcomes.

Asymptomatic potato seed tubers imported from Europe may serve as primary inoculum that changes the population structure of *Phytophthora infestans* in Israel

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Late blight caused by the oomycete *Phytophthora infestans* is a devastating disease of potato worldwide. In Israel, potatoes are grown twice a year, in autumn and spring. In both seasons late blight causes extensive damage. Tubers seeds for autumn planting are produced locally, but those for spring planting are imported from Europe. The present study shows that seed tubers imported for the spring season may carry EU genotypes of the pathogen, which eventually change the population structure of the pathogen in the country. A small percentage of the imported tubers (1.2-2.5%, in different years/cultivars) show no external symptoms of the disease but carry asymptomatic infection with late blight. Asymptomatic tubers produce infected sprouts at about one month after planting (1) which serve as primary inoculum for foliage attack. When such infected plants are uprooted from soil and the seed tubers sterilized and sliced, profuse sporulation of *P. infestans* develops on the slices after incubation in moist conditions for 1-2 days. While the dominant genotype of *P. infestans* in the autumn season in Israel is 23A1, the genotypes in the following spring change to include also 13A2 or 36A2. Interestingly, the emigrated genotypes do not persist to the next autumn season, allowing 23A1 to again predominant the population. Our long-term monitoring data suggest that the population structure of *P. infestans* changes yearly, but temporarily, due to the emigration of new genotypes from Europe.

1. Johnson, D. A., and Cummings, T. F. 2009. Latent infection of potato seed tubers by *Phytophthora infestans* during long-term cold storage. Plant Dis. 93:940-946.

Permanent Spraying System for controlling foliar diseases in apple

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Apple is one of the most important crops in the Galilee-Golan region. Apple trees are susceptible to foliar diseases such as scab, powdery mildew, and fruit rot. In addition, Moldy core disease attacks Red Delicious varieties during flowering with no effective control. Traditional disease management involves spraying fungicides using tractor-pulled sprayers, incurring high costs and practical limitations. We evaluated the use of sprinklers over the canopies as a permanent spraying system (PSS) employing a new technology of Pulsar sprinkler, which allows working with low rates and low doses, as used with pesticides. Using an irrigation computer and a fertilizer pump, we timed the spraying to coincide with susceptible periods. Experiments conducted during five years (2019-2023) in apple orchards evaluated the efficacy of sprinkling fungicides against various diseases, compared to commercial sprayers and untreated trees. Fungicide application through PSS for 10 minutes at 7-14 d intervals significantly reduced the incidence and severity of powdery mildew and scab on leaves and fruits by 90-100%, and calyx rot in cv. Pink Lady by 70-80%, compared to untreated trees. PSS treatments were similar or more effective than commercial tractor spraying. Applying fungicides to apple blossoms of cv. Red Delicious 2-3 times a day for 10 minutes each, during the flowering period, reduced fruits with moldy core by 65-85%. PSS greatly reduced pesticide drift compared blower sprayer. The use of PSS holds the potential to reduce pesticide usage, decrease grower expenses, and enhance targeting and precision in application.

Climate changing and plant parasitic nematodes – risk analysis under global warming

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Research interest in the mechanisms enabling plant-parasitic nematodes to adjust their physiological performance and cope with changing temperatures has intensified in light of global warming. Here, we show that geographically distinct populations of the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita*, prevalent in the three main pepper-growing regions in Israel—Carmel Valley (Carmel), Jordan Valley (JV), and the Arava Rift (Arava)—possess persistent differences in their thermal acclimation capacity, which affect embryonic development. The optimal temperature for embryonic growth completion for Carmel population was 25°C, 25 and 30°C for JV population, and 30°C for Arava population. Studying temperature dependent penetration, Carmel population demonstrated increased J2s penetration at 25°C compared to JV and Arava populations, the opposite trend was found at 33°C, where increased penetration of tomato roots was observed for the Arava population compared to the Carmel and JV populations. Next, for studying the molecular mechanism underlying population's thermal adaption, we performed transcriptomic analysis. RNA of infected roots at 25, 30, and 33°C was extracted and sequenced using Illumina sequencing PE150, which identified an extensive set of genes in different populations cultured under different temperatures. Gene ontology and KEGG-pathway-based analysis were used to further investigate the functions of the differentially expressed genes (DEGs). Results so far indicate that Carmel population possess higher plasticity compared with Arava, as reflected by significant increase in differential expressed genes along the temperatures. The transcriptome profiles presented in this study provide insight into the transcriptome complexity and will contribute to further understanding thermal adaptation under temperature change scenarios.

Reduction of the microbial load in Medjool dates after harvest

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Medjool dates are in high demand but some importer countries require microbial load to be below a set threshold. The research objective was therefore to identify methods to reduce the microbial load of Medjool dates after harvest. Medjool dates were retrieved from The Jordan Valley during 3 seasons and were treated after harvest with ethanol fumes, cold-plasma applicator of hydrogen peroxide, a commercial formulation of peracetic acid or ozonated water. Treatment with ethanol fumes for 20 hours reduced fungal load by 2 orders of magnitude but had minor effect on bacterial load. The ethanol fumigation treatment was also effective when carried out after 6 month of freeze storage. Treatment with hydrogen peroxide reduced bacterial load but showed peel damage that recovered after shelf life in one experiment but not in another. Similar levels of external and internal of microbial load were found and microbial load was slightly higher in the blossom end as compared to the stem-end. Sequencing of fungal DNA in the dates showed that *Aspergillus* was the predominant fungal genus while *Bacillus* was the dominant genus after shelf life. The treatment with ethanol fumes changed the volatile profile of the dates but did not have an apparent influence of their flavor. The treatment with ethanol fumes was successfully implemented on other date products and by in-package release but further assessment of the technology is required under commercial conditions.

Rapid, direct, and sequence-specific identification of RNA viruses in various crop plants using CRISPR/Cas13a

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Plant viruses are destructive pathogens causing significant damage to various crop species. Rapid, sensitive, and specific detection is crucial for the effective containment of emerging and resistance-breaking viruses. CRISPR/Cas has been established as a useful tool for plant virus identification. However, its application for on-site, direct detection of viruses from plant tissues is still limited. In this study, we present a rapid method for detecting viruses directly from RNA of different crop species using CRISPR/Cas13a. We successfully applied this method to identify tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) in infected tomato plants and differentiate it from closely related tobamoviruses. ToBRFV could be identified in a 100-fold dilution and early during infection, prior to the onset of viral symptoms. Moreover, CRISPR/Cas13a was used to directly identify cucumber green mottle mosaic virus (CGMMV) in cucumber plants and turnip mosaic virus (TuMV) in *Brassica napus* plants. Finally, we developed a user-friendly, extraction-free, 15-minute protocol for on-site ToBRFV identification using a portable fluorescent viewer and a mobile phone camera. This protocol was successfully applied for ToBRFV detection in a commercial greenhouse. These results demonstrate that CRISPR/Cas13a is a robust technology for direct, rapid, sensitive, and specific identification of multiple viruses in different crop plants that can be easily implemented for on-site detection.

The Potassium Phosphite-Based Fungicide Canon[®] Controls Basil Downy Mildew Under Greenhouse Conditions in Israel

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Sweet basil downy mildew (BDM), caused by *Peronospora belbahrii* is the most destructive disease of commercially produced sweet basil in Israel and, unless properly managed, may lead to 100% yield reduction. Four experiments were conducted over three growing seasons (fall 2021, fall 2022 and spring 2023) under commercial-like conditions to determine the efficacy of the phosphonic acid-based fungicide Canon following a conservative, seven-day protective spraying protocol. While Canon did not eradicate the pathogen, treated plants had 41 to 99.9% less ($P < 0.05$) disease incidence and / or severity than the untreated control plants. The disease scores on plants treated with Canon were similar ($P > 0.05$) to an alternation of Revus (a.i. mandipropamid) / Cabrio (a.i. pyraclostrobin) in fall 2021; less ($P < 0.05$) than Revus in fall 2022 and higher ($P < 0.05$) than an alternation of Acrobat (a.i. dimethomorph) / Cabrio at the end of the spring 2023 experiment. The inhibitory effect of Canon, its short pre-harvest application interval and low cost compared to other fungicides make it an excellent addition and a potential replacement for controlling BDM under greenhouse conditions that should be further explored.

Looking for new effective products for the control of bulb&stem nematodes in Garlic

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Until few years ago it was rare to find garlic fields with significant damage caused by the bulb&stem nematodes *Ditylenchus dipsaci* in Israel. There are two registered products for the control of bulb&stem nematodes: Namacur and Bionem. Namacur is the only one in use, either in "dipping treatment" before planting and/or spraying in the field. In the 2022-2023 season there was a project, conducted in Mevo-Hama, to find new effective products to control bulb&stem nematodes in garlic. One trial was conducted in "Shani" variety, irrigated by sprinklers. The second trial was conducted in "Ori" variety irrigated by irrigation machine (walking pipe). In both trials there was mechanical planting and the cloves were dipped in Namacur solution before planting. In both trials there were 2-3 applications – the first 3-4 weeks after planting, the second 3-4 weeks later and the last (if given) after more than a month, according to the rain/irrigation possibilities. In both trials the visual damage to the plants, caused by the nematodes (either in the trials and in the commercial fields), started during March 2023. The most effective product for controlling the nematodes, was the "Vellum-Prime". In the "Vellum-Prime" treated plots there almost zero damage. In "Namacur" treated plots there was 40% efficacy in the early planting field (irrigation machine). In the later planted field, the "Namacur" supplied 80% control (sprinklers). There were other products with noticeable efficacy and maybe in the future we will find them in the use here.

Posters

***Candidatus* Liberibacter solanacearum infection alters phytohormone levels in carrot plants, which in turn regulate the expression of disease symptoms.**

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Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum (Lso) is an unculturable, intracellular, phloem-limited bacterial pathogen transmitted by insect vectors, psyllids. Lso Haplotype D (LsoD) is associated with the yellowing disease in Apiaceae, especially in carrots. Carrot infection by LsoD results in extensive axillary shoot proliferation leading to the well-known witches' broom phenotype, as well as to leaf discoloration, secondary root formation, tap root deformation and reduce the yield at the field level. As these symptoms are primarily of developmental nature, we wanted to examine the effect of Lso infection of carrot phytohormones and their effect on disease symptoms. We found that Lso infection alters the expression of genes involved in the synthesis and sensing of plant hormones, gibberellin and cytokinin (CK), but no change was seen in the expression of the genes involved in the biosynthesis and sensing of auxin. We further found that the level of different phytohormone, particularly CK, is significantly affected by Lso infection, and that change is seen in root tissues. Interestingly, application of CK to carrot plants infected with Lso significantly enhances the rate of witches' broom symptoms appearance as well as its severity compared with untreated plants. The application of auxin, on the other hand, led to a delay in the appearance of witches' broom symptoms but caused an increase in the development of lateral roots. Furthermore, CK application alone, in the absence of the pathogen, induces typical witches' broom symptoms, and auxin alone enhances lateral root growth. Results suggest Lso alters phytohormone levels, particularly cytokinin, contributing to the observed developmental symptoms.

Generating tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) resistance in tomato plants by mutagenesis of a host resistance gene

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Plant viruses of the *Tobamovirus* genus cause substantial agricultural losses and significantly impact the yield and quality of various crops. The Tobamovirus tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) poses a substantial threat on the global tomato industry. This virus overcomes the long-standing *Tm-2²* resistance (R) gene, which has been protecting tomato crops from tobamoviruses for over 60 years. *Tm-2²* encodes a plant immune receptor that recognizes the tobamovirus movement protein (MP), and thereby triggers a resistance termed hypersensitive response (HR), programmed cell death of the infected tissue that limits the virus from spreading. Previously in our lab, we found that *Tm-2²* fails to recognize the ToBRFV MP (MP^{ToBRFV}), and thereby fails to confer resistance. Previous studies showed that R genes can be altered to confer resistance against new pathogens. In the current study, we used directed evolution to isolate *Tm-2²* mutations potentially conferring ToBRFV resistance. To do so, a *Tm-2²* mutant library was generated. Each mutant was co-expressed with MP^{ToBRFV}. Appearance of HR-mediated necrosis indicated successful recognition and defense response. Out of 800 screened mutants, three *Tm-2²* variants with potential ToBRFV recognition were isolated. In this work, I generated transgenic tomato plants constitutively expressing these *Tm-2²* variants. Currently, I am testing these lines for ToBRFV resistance. My preliminary results indicate enhanced resistance response in specific lines. In addition, using CRISPR/Cas9, I am introducing mutations in a targeted region of *Tm-2²*, potentially involved in ToBRFV recognition. Ultimately, I aim to generate new tomato lines with improved resistance against ToBRFV.

Make it grow: *Moesziomyces aphidis* promotes plant growth

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Increasing global population requires more food supply and higher agricultural yield while avoiding the use of harmful products in agriculture. The use of beneficial microorganisms is an Eco-friendly approach to replace/reduce the use of harmful agricultural products. We isolated a unique *Moesziomyces aphidis* strain (L12) that has shown anti-microbial and plant growth promoting activity. *M. aphidis* is a yeast like dimorphic fungus related to the phytopathogenic fungus Ustilago. Unlike its relative, *M. aphidis* is not only non-pathogenic but rather beneficial to the host plant. *M. aphidis* secretes compounds that were found to have bioactive properties. We isolated the fraction with plant growth promoting activity and tested it on different plants. Tomato, melon and corn plants treated with our extract exhibited enhanced growth parameters and the tomato plants produced higher and better-quality yield. The pharmacological parameters of our fraction were tested and GCMS analysis was conducted to identify potentially bioactive compounds. We found that it contains siderophores and auxin like derivatives. Genomic analysis (RNAseq) of juvenile tomato plants treated with our extract was carried out in order to identify the growth mechanisms engaged by our extract. The transcriptome data revealed that our extract prompts mainly biological pathways related to plant growth and development.

Characterization of plant growth promoting activity, compounds and the mechanisms involved in interaction of beneficial microorganisms such as *M. aphidis* with host plants will enrich our knowledge. The data and insights from our research can promote the development of green products that can reduce harmful agricultural products usage.

***Fusarium* species composition in agricultural fields in northeastern Israel and its effect on the onion basal rot disease**

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Onion *Fusarium* basal rot (FBR) is a significant limitation to *Allium cepa* production worldwide. Here, the *Fusarium* population structure involved in the disease outburst was studied in two representative fields in northeast Israel, one in the Galilee (Hula Valley) and the second in the Golan Heights. Using colony morphology, microscopic taxonomic keys, and molecular methods, a new, unreported *Fusarium solani* species complex was discovered as a widely spread member of the *Fusarium* pathobiome community. This species appeared more generalist since it was found in all three onion cultivars' samples. It was also less virulent in seed germination (42-52% higher sprout biomass, $p < 0.05$) and bulb pathogenicity tests (41-45% less necrosis) than *Fusarium acutatum*. Whereas the Galilee yellow Orlando onion cultivar bulbs sampled are colonized by *F. solani* (70%) and two other, less abundant species, *F. oxysporum*, f. sp. *cepae*, and *F. acutatum* (15% each), the Golan Heights field's *Fusarium* community, show host specificity. Here, *F. oxysporum* f. sp. *cepae* inhabited the red onion Ha2 cultivar bulbs, whereas *F. acutatum* colonized the yellow Ha1 cultivar (40% and 50% prevalence along with *F. solani*). In addition, antagonistic and synergistic interactions within the *Fusarium* population exist among certain onion genotypes. A better understanding of this disease complexity caused by different *Fusarium* species with a divergence in host susceptibility and virulence is critical for developing disease management strategies. Since each *Fusarium* species reacts differently to pest control treatments, the changes in the species composition may require specifically adapted pest control solutions.

Effect of Temperature and Humidity on Mycelial Growth and Spore Germination of the Pathogenic Fungus *Alternaria alternata* Causing Black Spot Disease in Pomegranate

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Pomegranate black spot disease (PBSD) is caused by specific isolates of the fungus *Alternaria alternata*. The fungus induces necrotic spots that develop to round lesions on leaves and fruits early in the summer, impacting fruit quality and rendering them unsuitable for marketing. Understanding the environmental conditions necessary for pathogen infection and disease development is vital for devising eco-friendly prevention methods. This study investigates the impact of temperature and humidity on pathogen growth and spore germination of four PBSD isolates. Pathogen growth and spore germination were assessed *in vitro* across temperatures ranging from 5 to 35°C, with humidity duration tested at 10 and 20°C. Pathogenic and non-pathogenic isolates of *A. alternata*, obtained from mandarin and persimmon, were also tested for comparison. Lower cardinal temperatures for PBSD lesion growth ranged from 6.95 to 11.2°C, with optimal temperatures between 25.1 and 27.5°C, and upper cardinal temperatures from 35 to 38.5°C. Optimal spore germination temperatures for PBSD isolates fell within the range of 25-27°C, with germination occurring between 4-35°C. After 10 hours of humidity at 10°C, maximum germination reached approximately 60%, compared to nearly 100% at 20°C in all the isolates tested. Although results align with orchard conditions during symptom onset, no significant differences were observed in optimal conditions between PBSD isolates and other pathogenic isolates, or the saprophytic isolate. This suggests that PBSD isolate infectivity may be attributed to specific isolate traits rather than general temperature and humidity requirements.

Inheritance of resistance against downy mildew in cucumber

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Downy mildew caused by the oomycete *Pseudoperonospora cubensis* is a devastating disease of cucurbits worldwide. In Israel, pathotype 3 attacks cucumber and melon while pathotype 6, discovered in 2002 (1), attacks also squash, pumpkin and Dalorit. Unlike in other countries, watermelon, luffa and momordica are not affected by the disease. The inheritance of resistance to downy mildew in melon was found by us to be controlled by two complementary, partially dominant genes that are responsible for aminotransferase activity in the peroxisome (2). Resistant commercial melon cultivars are now available on the market. No resistant cultivars of cucumber are available in Israel. In the present research we examined the resistance against multiple isolates of *P. cubensis* in two wild cucumber accessions, PI 197088, and PI 330628. F1 hybrid plants of a cross between the susceptible SMR18 and each resistant accession exhibited moderate resistance to downy mildew suggesting partial dominant gene(s). However, F2 plants inoculated in the field showed extremely variable response to the disease, ranging from full susceptibility to complete resistance. Furthermore, the ratio between S, MR and R plants was isolate-dependent (3), suggesting multiple minor genes for resistance (QTLs). DNA was extracted for QTL analyses from 180 plants of two F2 segregating families that were each inoculated in the field with mixed isolates of the pathogen. The results confirmed that QTLs are harbored on chromosomes 4 and 5. Several cycles of backcrossing to elite lines of cucumbers have yielded resistant breeding lines, type Bet Alpha or slicer, with adequate horticultural traits, such as femaleness, parthenocarpy, fruit shape and fruit color.

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Breeding of Medical Cannabis for Disease Resistance

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Cannabis sativa is an economically important medical plant. In Israel, about two thousand patients are treated with oil or flowers of cannabis to relief pain and disease. However, cannabis plants suffer of various diseases. Among the most important ones are powdery mildew (PM) caused by the fungus *Golovinomyces cichoracearum* and grey mold (GM) caused by the fungus *Botrytis cinerea*. The former pathogen attacks the foliage during growth and the later pathogen attacks the foliage during growth, and the female inflorescences during growth and storage. In the present study, we identified low-quality cannabis lines that exhibited resistance against PM or GM. We crossed these lines and combined both resistances in pedigree lines. In parallel, by using EMS, we created artificial mutant plants of Hemp (*Cannabis sativa* with low content of cannabinoids) that exhibited resistance to both PM and GM. The resistant plants (natural and mutants) were each crossed with elite cannabis susceptible lines. After several cycles of backcrossing, we obtained BC3F2 and BC4F2 lines that exhibited full resistance against both diseases. Current crosses are aimed to improve plants architecture, content of cannabinoids (CBD, THC) and shape of the female inflorescences.

Studying the Etiology of Postharvest Decay of Long-Term Stored Carrots the Development of Sustainable Control Measures

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On 2022, the fungicide Rovral[®] (a.i. Iprodione 50%) was banned for use as postharvest treatment before long-term cold-storage of carrots (0-2°C for 6-10 months) and was replaced by the fungicide Scholar[®] (a.i. Fludioxonil 230 SC). Subsequently, reports of molds and rots in stored carrots increased. The goal of this research is to identify the pathogens causing carrot decay in cold storage, in order to develop and fine-tune sustainable diseases control methods. To this aim, 24 fungal isolates were collected from infected carrots from various commercial warehouses in Israel. Initial molecular identification was conducted using ITS-1,4 primers, followed by analysis of specific primer sets for each of the pathogens. The main pathogens that were identified included *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* (White Mold), *Botrytis cinerea* (Grey mold), *Geotrichum candidum* (Sour rot), and *Alternaria tenuissima* (Black spot). Pathogenicity was evaluated at 5 and 16°C, and was followed by completion of Koch's postulates. Furthermore, growth inhibition by Rovral[®] and Scholar[®] was determined on poisoned agar media, identifying several *S. sclerotiorum* with reduced sensitivity to Rovral[®] at 1 ppm, or resistance to both Rovral[®] and Scholar[®] at 100 ppm. Future research will investigate resistance mechanisms in *Botrytis* and *Sclerotinia* strains using molecular and physiological approaches. Uncovering resistance mechanisms of postharvest pathogens of carrot, alongside testing combinations of inorganic GRAS salts with Scholar[®], would facilitate sustainable disease management to mitigate postharvest losses, while reducing the selective pressure for the development of resistance to Fludioxonil.

Elevated temperatures suppress autoimmunity in melon mutant plants without inducing susceptibility in resistant WT plants.

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Understanding plant immunity mechanisms at higher temperatures is key to mitigating the impacts of climate change on food security. In melon, the dominant *Prv* gene encodes a Nucleotide-binding, leucine-rich repeat receptor (NLR) protein and provides resistance to *Papaya Ringspot Virus (PRSV)*. Through CRISPR/Cas9 mutagenesis of a PRSV-resistant genotype, we obtained several inactivated alleles. The mutant progeny became susceptible, demonstrating the functionality of the candidate gene. One mutated allele, *prvΔ154*, is susceptible to *PRSV* and encoded a truncated product. *prvΔ154* exhibited extreme dwarfism, along with leaf lesions, cell death, high salicylic acid levels, and elevated defense gene expression. Elevated temperatures can negatively regulate plant immune responses and generate susceptibility to pathogen infection. As observed in other autoimmune mutants, the *prvΔ154* autoimmune phenotype was evident at 25 °C but was inhibited at a higher temperature (32 °C). Because *prvΔ154* autoimmunity was suppressed at higher temperatures, we speculate that higher temperatures may induce susceptibility to PRSV in wild-type plants. Remarkably, wild-type (WT) plants possessing a functional *Prv* allele sustained their resistance to PRSV at temperatures reaching up to 40 °C, a common condition in melon-growing areas. In conclusion, our observations suggest that the *prvΔ154* autoimmune response is qualitatively different from the WT response to *PRSV*, which is controlled by *Prv*. This is further supported by the susceptibility of *prvΔ154* to *PRSV*.

Potential use of bacteriophages as biocontrol agents against the plant pathogen *Acidovorax citrulli*

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Acidovorax citrulli is the causal agent of bacterial fruit blotch (BFB), a disease that significantly impacts the production of cucurbit crops, mainly melons and watermelons. The predominant management strategy for BFB involves spraying copper-based bactericides, which pose environmental risks and promote the emergence of resistant *A. citrulli* strains. This emphasizes the need for novel, environmentally friendly disease management approaches that minimize reliance on harmful chemical pesticides. Recent studies have identified bacteriophages (phages) as potential biocontrol agents, offering a sustainable alternative for controlling plant pathogens within integrated pest management systems. Our research aims to explore the application of environmental phage isolates as biocontrol agents against *A. citrulli*. Through environmental sampling, we isolated phages showing specific lytic activity against *Acidovorax* spp. strains. Phage characterization included host range analysis, bactericidal properties, and genetic profiling. Host range analysis revealed that the isolated phages target a variety of *A. citrulli* strains with few of them targeting other plant-pathogenic *Acidovorax* spp. Selected isolates were assessed for their bactericidal properties using killing curves, revealing variable efficacy in inhibiting bacterial growth over time. This efficacy was dependent on the ratio between phage and bacteria, as tested in a plate reader assay. We are currently characterizing selected phages by whole genome sequencing and microscopy analysis (SEM/TEM). Phages exhibiting the most promising results in terms of ability to exterminate *A. citrulli* strains *in vitro* will be tested *in planta* to evaluate their potential to reduce BFB damage.

The Spread and Colonization Dynamics of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Sensitive, Resistant, and Non-Almond Plants at the Leaf Level in Almond Trees

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The bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* causes numerous diseases that lead to significant damage to agricultural crops worldwide. Almond leaf scorch disease was first reported in Israel in 2017, in the Hula Valley in the north. In 2020, we conducted a survey of almond varieties and found a resistant strain to the disease, which we began to investigate to understand the source of its resistance. In this experiment, we examined the survival, multiplication and movement of the bacterium within the resistant cultivar. To do this, we introduced, using needle, fluorescently labeled *Xylella fastidiosa* bacteria into petioles of three different varieties: a sensitive almond variety, a resistant one, and a non-host variety (plum), and we examined the distribution of the bacterium using microscopy, isolations, and qPCR up to 100 days after inoculation (dai). The leaves were cut at fixed distances from the point of inoculation (POI), the results show that *Xylella* did spread within the leaf of the resistant and non-host plants but mainly along the xylem stream, indicating passive progression. The total average infection rate was 97% in the sensitive and 37% and 18% in the resistant and non-host plants respectively, with 2 times higher colonized vessels in the sensitive compared to the resistant and 8 times higher compared to the non-host. Isolations of live bacteria from the sensitive plant reached 100% success, while the resistant and non-host strains reached only 33%, and the bacteria population in the plant tissue (CFU g⁻¹) was significantly lower (2 orders of magnitude). qPCR analysis showed higher percentages of positive samples and higher bacterial concentrations (CT values) in the sensitive plant. No symptoms were observed in the resistant and non-host plants, while symptoms were evident in the sensitive plant as early as 30 dai. These results suggest that the resistance may come from the *Xylella*'s inability to survive within and progress between vessels over time. This may be related to the structure and the bacterium's known ability to degrade vessels to advance. Further research on vessel structure among different varieties, both microscopically and genetically, is currently underway, and its findings will shed light on this issue and help us better understand the Host specificity of *Xylella*.